

Synergistic role of graphene and carbon nanotubes in improving the toughness of alumina/zirconia ceramic hybrid nanocomposite

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Abstract:

Ceramic-based composite materials are attractive for the jet engines, spacecraft, power generation machines as well as military armors applications, however, intrinsic brittleness limits their use for aforesaid technologies [1, 2]. In this study, the synergistic influence of GNT inclusions (graphene and carbon nanotube) on the microstructure development and mechanical properties of the alumina/zirconia ceramic hybrid nanocomposite was investigated. The homogeneous GNT inclusions dispersion and hot-pressing method cumulatively led hybrid nanocomposite to near theoretical densification and fine-grained microstructure. The GNT inclusions induced pullout and crack-bridging toughening mechanisms utilizing their characteristic geometries in the final hybrid nanocomposites. The resulting hybrid nanocomposite demonstrated enhanced fracture toughness by 205 and 102 % and microhardness by 19 and 30% over the monolithic alumina and alumina/zirconia nanocomposites, respectively. The reinforcing ability of the GNT inclusions in the hybrid nanocomposite was probed using the information extracted from the advanced microscope and proven qualitative methods. Further, the toughening mechanism offered by the GNT inclusion in the hybrid nanocomposites was further understood by outlining a schematic model and thoroughly discussed.

Keywords:

Graphene, Hybrid nanocomposites, Smart materials, Alumina ceramic, nanostructure

Figure 1: SEM images of a fractured AZGNT hybrid nanocomposite showing the interaction of GNT inclusions with the matrix grains, (b) short CNT pullout, (c) large CNT pullout and (d) wrapping of matrix grains by a GNP segment..

References:

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2. Ahmad, I., Islam, M., Zhu, Y.Q., (2015) Toughening mechanisms and mechanical properties of graphene nanosheet reinforced alumina, Materials and Design.